

TREATMENT OF MICE WITH TLR4 AND IFN- γ ANTIBODY AND EXOGENOUS IL-10 MODULATES BCL2 AND LC3 EXPRESSION IN RANKL/M-CSF PLUS LPS STIMULATED BONE MARROW MACROPHAGES- LEADING TO BONE RESORPTION

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ABSTRACT

Bone marrow derived macrophages activation must be precisely regulated to ensure an effective immune response to infectious agents while preventing excessive inflammation and associated toxicity. Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) is activated by lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from Gram-negative bacteria, initiating pro-inflammatory signaling cascades leading to bone damage. Moreover, LPS-induced cellular autophagy plays a critical role in osteoclastogenesis and bone resorption, primarily through the LC3-mediated pathway. Whereas, elevated levels of the anti-apoptotic protein BCL2 can counteract this effect and restore bone integrity. Our study demonstrates that treatment with TLR4 antibody (TLR4Ab) and IFN- γ antibody (IFN γ Ab), combined with exogenous IL-10 in LPS induced bone damage model, effectively downregulates cellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to suppressed mTOR expression and subsequent regulation of pro-inflammatory cytokine production in LPS stimulated bone marrow macrophages. Moreover, dual antibody treatment prior to LPS induced bone damage and post-IL-10 administration restores the phagocytic capacity of undifferentiated RBMCs as evidenced by improved

macrophages. Moreover, dual antibody treatment prior to LPS induced bone damage and post-IL-10 administration restores the phagocytic capacity of undifferentiated RBMCs as evidenced by improved

membrane fluidity and bacterial engulfment. These findings highlight the therapeutic potential of targeting TLR4 and IFN γ , along with IL-10 supplementation, to mitigate LPS-induced bone inflammation by suppressing autophagy-driven osteoclastogenesis. This approach offers a promising strategy for preventing bacterial infection-associated bone loss and warrants further investigation as a potential therapeutic intervention in inflammatory bone diseases.

KEYWORDS: Bone resorption; Lipopolysaccharide; TLR4, IFN γ , Autophagy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The skeletal system is in a constant state of bone remodeling, a process in which old or damaged bone is substituted with new bone. This ongoing renewal is mainly controlled by osteoclasts, which are involved in the resorption of bone tissue, and osteoblasts, which play a crucial role in the formation of new bone.^[1] Toll-like receptors (TLRs) function as essential pattern recognition receptors, facilitating the identification of a wide array of microbial structures. In particular, TLR2 is responsible for recognizing the structural components of Gram-positive bacteria, whereas the TLR4 receptor complex is attuned to detect lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from Gram-negative bacteria.^[2] The signaling pathways activated by TLRs are vital for maintaining bone homeostasis through both direct and indirect pathways. Indirectly, the activation of TLRs triggers the release of inflammatory cytokines, which contribute to bone loss. Osteoblasts, which express TLRs,^[3] play a significant role in this process by producing pro-inflammatory cytokines that stimulate osteoclast activation, leading to increased bone resorption. Additionally, the inhibition of osteogenic differentiation due to inflammation further intensifies inflammatory bone loss, underscoring the complex relationship between the immune system and skeletal remodeling. The regulatory function of interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) in the differentiation of osteoclasts and osteoblasts has been the subject of extensive research, revealing its effects are dependent on the specific context. Studies have shown that IFN- γ facilitates the degradation of TNF receptor-associated factor 6 (TRAF6) during RANKL-induced osteoclastogenesis, thereby influencing osteoclast differentiation.^[4] Nevertheless, the effects of IFN- γ on osteoclastogenesis are shaped by various factors, including the levels of IFN- γ , RANKL, and macrophage colony-stimulating factor (M-CSF), as well as the duration of exposure and the differentiation stage of osteoclast precursors.^[5] These factors contribute to the inconsistencies observed in the regulation of

osteoclast function by IFN- γ , underscoring the complexity of its role in maintaining bone homeostasis.

Numerous cell biological studies have aimed to identify intracellular signaling molecules that contribute to the regulation of osteoclastic activity. Among these, reactive oxygen species (ROS), particularly superoxide anions ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), have been implicated in the bone resorption process by facilitating matrix degradation. To investigate the role of ROS in osteoclast activation, Bax et al. examined the effects of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) a relatively stable ROS—on bone resorption using freshly isolated rat osteoclasts. Their findings demonstrated that nanomolar concentrations of H_2O_2 significantly stimulated osteoclastic bone resorption and enhanced osteoclast motility, suggesting that ROS may function as critical mediators in the regulation of osteoclast activity.^[6] Lysozyme has the ability to bound--- with LPS and reduced the lethal toxicity and the biological activity of LPS.^[7]

Phagocytic cells, which include neutrophils, monocytes, and macrophages, are essential elements of the innate immune system. Among these, macrophages are particularly significant in the process of phagocytosis, aiding in the intracellular breakdown of antigens such as LPS and apoptotic cells. Activated macrophages contribute to immune responses through multiple mechanisms, including phagocytosis, the production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, and the synthesis and release of nitric oxide (NO).^[8] The cellular response to bacterial pathogens and other antigens is a critical component of the host defense mechanism. The experimental outcomes from this study demonstrated satisfactory cellular responses, supporting the establishment of the immunomodulatory effects of dual antibody treatment in conjunction with interleukin-10 (IL-10).

Exposure to LPS leads to the upregulation of interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), which is essential for regulating the inflammatory response and bone metabolism. This mechanism involves the recruitment and activation of osteoclasts, the specialized cells responsible for the degradation of bone tissue.^[9] Prior research has shown that LPS exposure results in a marked increase in IL-1 β mRNA levels, peaking around 4 hours after exposure, indicating a swift and vigorous initial reaction to LPS-induced inflammation.^[10] The IL-1 receptor (IL-1R) comprises a Toll-IL-1 receptor (TIR) domain within the IL-1RI–IL-1R accessory protein (IL-1RAcP) complex, which recruits MyD88 to trigger intracellular signaling pathways.^[11] This activation leads to downstream inflammatory responses that facilitate osteoclast differentiation and bone resorption.

In addition to IL-1, tumor necrosis factor (TNF), which includes TNF- α and TNF- β , shares both structural and functional characteristics^[12] with IL-1 and signals through two distinct receptors: TNF receptor 1 (TNF-R1) and TNF receptor 2 (TNF-R2). Notably, TNF-R1 is primarily responsible for the pro-inflammatory and catabolic effects of TNF.^[13,14] Our previous studies have indicated a significant increase in TNF-R1 expression following LPS stimulation, underscoring its importance in the inflammatory signaling pathway.^[15]

Both IL-1 and TNF exhibit overlapping biological functions, particularly in their capacity to stimulate bone resorption. These cytokines promote osteoclastogenesis directly by encouraging the proliferation of osteoclast progenitors and indirectly by enhancing the resorptive capabilities of mature osteoclasts.^[16] Importantly, IL-1 and TNF are often co-expressed *in vivo*, working synergistically to enhance bone-resorptive activity and contributing to pathological bone loss in inflammatory conditions.

Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) is a serine/threonine protein kinase that regulates cell growth, proliferation, and survival in response to environmental stimuli. Studies by Zhang *et al.* have demonstrated that the activation of mTOR complex 1 (mTORC1) in the synovium promotes M1 macrophage polarization, thereby exacerbating the symptoms of collagenase-induced osteoarthritis (CIOA).^[17] In the context of LPS mediated inflammation, LPS binding to TLR4 and receptor RANKL interaction with RANK initiate a signaling cascade that activates mTOR, subsequently modulating inflammatory responses and osteoclastogenesis. Separately, signal transducer and activator of transcription 5 (STAT5) plays a crucial role in osteoclast differentiation, particularly via cytokines such as interleukin-7 (IL-7). Unlike RANKL-dependent osteoclastogenesis, IL-7 induces osteoclast formation through STAT5 activation in a RANKL-independent manner.^[18] Additionally, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF) serves as a potent activator of STAT5, further emphasizing its role in the regulation of bone homeostasis and immune function.^[19]

In this context, earlier studies have indicated that transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1) functions as a negative regulator in inflammatory responses. While septic shock induced by LPS is driven by endogenous inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1, the inhibitory role of TGF- β 1 is essential for the survival of cells.^[20]

It is widely recognized that RANKL primarily promotes osteoclastogenesis through the signaling pathway of c-Jun N-terminal kinase 1 (JNK1).^[21] Beyond the well-documented c-

Jun/AP-1 pathway, recent studies indicate that a BCL2 autophagy activation pathway may also be involved in JNK1-mediated osteoclast differentiation.^[22] BCL2, an essential anti-apoptotic protein, has a dual function in osteoclastogenesis by modulating both autophagy and apoptosis. While the phosphorylation of BCL2 is known to trigger autophagic processes, it can also promote apoptosis concurrently. As a pro-survival factor, BCL2 interacts with BAX and other pro-apoptotic proteins, thereby preventing the permeabilization of the mitochondrial membrane and inhibiting apoptosis. However, when BCL2 is phosphorylated, it allows for the dissociation of BAX from the BCL2-BAX complex, which activates apoptotic pathways.^[23] Additionally, the microtubule-associated protein 1 light chain 3 (LC3), a well-established marker of autophagy, exists in two forms: LC3-I (the cytosolic variant) and LC3-II (the lipidated variant). The transformation of LC3-I into LC3-II indicates the activation of autophagy. Research has shown an increase in LC3-II levels during RANKL-induced osteoclastogenesis, underscoring its significance in osteoclast differentiation. Nevertheless, experiments involving the knockdown of LC3 using small interfering RNA (siRNA) demonstrated minimal impact on osteoclastogenesis, suggesting that LC3's primary role is in facilitating actin ring formation rather than directly influencing osteoclast differentiation. These results imply that LC3 is crucial for bone resorption by aiding in the cytoskeletal organization essential for osteoclast functionality.^[24] Numerous studies have investigated the LC3-mediated autophagy pathway in various types of macrophages. However, there is a lack of research specifically examining the correlation between LC3 and BCL2 in bone marrow-derived macrophages and their role in modulating bone resorption. The potential regulatory interplay between autophagy and apoptosis in the context of LPS-induced osteoclastogenesis remains largely unexplored.

Keeping with this background we are curious to find out whether prior treatment of mice in LPS induced bone damage model with TLR4 and IFN γ antibody and exogenous IL-10 could alter the BCL2 and LC3 expression in RANKL/M-CSF plus LPS stimulated bone marrow macrophages leading to amelioration of LPS induced bone inflammation. However, no prior studies have been located that address this particular context. In light of the aforementioned hypothesis, this study has shown that treatment of LPS induced bone inflammation mice with TLR4 and IFN γ antibody and exogenous IL-10 could modulate BCL2 and LC3 expression in RANKL/M-CSF plus LPS stimulated bone marrow macrophages suggesting to bone resorption. Furthermore, the distinct functions of BCL2 and LC-3 in

relation to autophagy and apoptosis-mediated osteoclastogenesis, along with the mechanisms involved, necessitate additional research.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Maintenance of animals

All animal experiments were carried out in accordance with the protocols approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of the Department of Physiology at the University of Calcutta. This was conducted under the supervision of the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), with Approval Number: IAEC-V/T/BB-16/2024, dated March 20, 2024. The oversight was provided by the Committee of the Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying (DAHD), under the Ministry of Fisheries, Animal Husbandry and Dairying (MoFAH&D), Government of India. The study utilized male Swiss albino mice exclusively. Resident bone marrow cells (RBMCs) were isolated from the femurs of mice that had been administered LPS and antibodies.

2.2. Antibody pre-treatment and isolation of murine resident bone marrow cells for *in vitro* culture

Mice were pre-treated with antibodies against TLR4 (30 mg/kg)^[25] and IFN γ (6.6 mg/kg)^[26] 24hrs before LPS (5 mg/kg)^[27] administration. Subsequently, animals were supplemented with IL-10 (0.02 mg/kg)^[28] at 24hrs post LPS and then sacrificed at 3 days post LPS treatment.

For murine resident bone marrow cells; femurs were obtained from 6 to 12 weeks old Swiss albino mice with grouping of Control, LPS, TLR4Ab+LPS, IFN γ Ab+LPS, TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS, TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10, LPS+IL-10, TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10, IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10, TLR4Ab +IFN γ Ab+IL-10[where n=3]. The femurs were placed in 70 % ethanol for 1 min, washed in sterile DMEM and then both epiphyses were removed using sterile scissors and forceps. The bones were flushed with a 24Gz syringe filled with DMEM to extrude bone marrow. The cell suspension generated thereafter is called fresh bone marrow cells. Fresh bone marrow cells (FBMCs) were centrifuged 5 min at 200 \times g at 4°C and gently resuspended to obtain a solution containing from 4 to 6 $\times 10^6$ cells/ml in DMEM media containing 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS). After preparation these murine RBMCs from different treatment groups (4 $\times 10^6$ cells/ml), were cultured for 3 days at 37°C with 5% CO₂ stimulated with LPS (100 ng/ml)^[29] in the presence of RANKL (10 ng/ml) and M-CSF (10 ng/ml) to differentiate into bone marrow derived macrophages.^[30]

Figure 1: Flow chart of experimental work.

2.3. MTT assay for detection of cell viability

The MTT assay was conducted to assess the viability of the isolated RBMCs (before and after 3 days culture). A volume of 100 μ l of the cell sample (5×10^6 cells/ml) was placed in each well of a 96-well plate. Subsequently, 10 μ l of MTT reagent (1 mg/ml) was introduced to each well, followed by incubation in the dark at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 60 minutes. After this incubation period, the supernatant was carefully removed, and 200 μ l of Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) solution was added to each well, followed by an additional incubation of 10 minutes. The plates were then agitated for 15 minutes, and the optical density of each well was measured at a wavelength of 570 nm using a microplate reader. Percentage viability was calculated according to the formula: % cell viability = (Absorbance of sample / Absorbance of control) \times 100.^[31]

2.4. Measurement of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) production in RBMCs obtained from both LPS-stimulated and treatment groups following 3 days of cell culture

For this assay, a cell suspension was prepared with a concentration of 5×10^6 cells/ml. In addition to the previously mentioned pre-treatment and stimulation, 100 μ l of HRP (50 μ g/ml) and 100 μ l of Phenol red (0.02 mg/ml) were added to 200 μ l of the live cell suspension and incubated at 37 °C for 60 minutes. Following incubation, the supernatant was

collected after centrifugation, and the reaction was halted by the addition of 25 μl of 2N NaOH. The samples were then measured at 610 nm against a blank (which did not contain cells).^[32] The production of H_2O_2 was quantified and expressed as $\mu\text{M}/10^6$ cells. A standard curve for H_2O_2 was generated to assess the release of H_2O_2 .

2.5. Assessment of nitric oxide (NO) levels in RBMCs obtained from various groups of mice following a 3 days culture period

A total of 100 μl of cell culture supernatants from 100 μl of various in-vitro pre-treated and stimulated macrophage cell suspensions (5×10^6 cells/ml) were collected and combined with an equal volume of Griess reagent (comprising 1% sulfanilamide, 0.1% N-1-naphthylethylene diaminedihydrochloride in 5% phosphoric acid) for a duration of 10 minutes. The absorbance was subsequently measured at 492 nm, using the same volume of PBS and Griess reagent as a reference.^[33] The amount of nitric oxide (NO) produced was quantified as $\mu\text{M}/10^6$ cells. A modified NaNO_3 standard curve was utilized to facilitate the calculation of total NO production.

2.6. Assessment of superoxide anion (O_2^-) levels in RBMCs obtained from various groups of mice following a 3 days culture period

100 μl of live cell suspension (5×10^6 cells/ml) were incubated followed by LPS stimulation in the presence of cytochrome C (100 μL at 2 mg/ml conc.). The production of superoxide anion was recorded spectrophotometrically at 550nm with respect to the blank. The production of superoxide anion was calculated by using the following formula
nanomoles of superoxide anion = (mean absorbance at 550nm $\times 15.87$).^[34] After calculating the nanomoles of superoxide anion the results were expressed as $\text{nm}/10^6$ cells in Mean \pm SD form.

2.7. Measurement of Cellular Lysosomal Enzyme Activity from the RBMCs of different group of mice

Lysozyme activity was evaluated by determining the initial lysis rate of a *Micrococcus lysodeikticus* suspension. A lyophilized sample of *M. lysodeikticus* (5 mg) was reconstituted in 0.15 M potassium-phosphate buffer (pH 6.2) at room temperature to achieve an absorbance reading between 0.6 and 0.7 at 450 nm. This optical density can be fine-tuned by adding additional buffer or more *M. lysodeikticus* as needed just before the experiment. Subsequently, 900 μl of the prepared suspension was combined with 100 μl of cell-free lysate from RBMCs derived from various experimental groups, and the kinetic changes in optical

density were recorded immediately over a period of 60 seconds. The changes in absorbance during the first minute were used to determine the reaction rate. A single unit of enzyme is defined as the amount that causes a decrease in absorbance of 0.001 per minute at a wavelength of 450 nm.^[35] The specific activity of lysozyme was then calculated from a standard curve (using pure Lysozyme sigma) and reported as Units/mg of protein, presented as Mean \pm SD.

2.8. Assessment of the membrane fluidity of RBMCs for overall phagocytic activity

To further evaluate macrophage membrane fluidity, the Neutral Red Phagocytosis Assay was employed. This assay confirmed the complete phagocytic activity, including efficient schizolysis of target cells and the subsequent release of phagotropic neutral red, indicating effective intracellular processing of antigens. The assay was performed based on the neutral red uptake ability of the cells, as previously described^[36], with slight modifications. In brief, 100 μ l of RBMCs at a concentration of 5×10^6 cells/ml from various groups were placed in a 96-well plate. The supernatant was carefully discarded, and 100 μ l of 0.075% neutral red was added to each well, followed by a co-incubation period of 30 minutes at 37°C. After this, the wells were aspirated and washed three times with 200 μ l of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The cells were then lysed with 100 μ l per well of a 1:1 (v/v) solution of 100 mM acetic acid and dehydrated alcohol, and the plates were incubated for 8 hours at 4°C to facilitate complete cell lysis and the release of phagocytic neutral red. The optical density was measured at 490 nm using a microplate reader, with phagocytosis quantified as optical density (OD) values. The higher the OD value it corresponds to the higher membrane fluidity. The results were expressed as Mean OD \pm SD.

2.9. Preparation of live *S.aureus* suspension

Coagulase-positive and MRSA strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* were generously supplied by Professor Mausumi Sikdar (née Bhakta) from Presidency University in Kolkata, West Bengal, India. These strains are stored in our laboratory (PU-CA-14) and were cultured overnight in nutrient broth using a shaker.^[37] The proliferated bacteria were collected via centrifugation, and the resulting pellet was washed three times with PBS. The bacterial concentration was adjusted to reach the desired inoculum by setting the optical density to 0.2 at 620 nm, as determined by a spectrophotometer, which corresponds to 5×10^6 cells/ml for *Staphylococcus aureus*. To determine the colony-forming unit (CFU) count of the specified inoculum, the serial dilution method was utilized in conjunction with blood agar culture

medium.^[38] The findings from the biochemical and disc diffusion assays reveal that *S. aureus* tests positive for both coagulase and catalase, while also showing resistance to Gentamycin.

2.10. Bactericidal activity of RBMCs

To investigate the bactericidal activity of resident bone marrow-derived macrophages, the MTT colorimetric microassay was utilized. This method provided a quantitative assessment of macrophage-mediated bacterial killing.^[39] A total of 100 μ l of cell suspension (5×10^6 cells/ml) in DMEM from various treatment groups was mixed with 33.33 μ l of a live *S. aureus* suspension (3×10^8 CFU/ml), maintaining a bacteria to macrophage ratio of 10:1, along with 5% FBS. This combination was incubated at 37°C for one hour in a 96-well microtiter plate. Control samples consisted of: (i) macrophages in culture medium, which showed a 90% killing efficiency, and (ii) bacteria in culture medium, which exhibited a 0% killing efficiency. After the incubation, macrophages were lysed by adding 50 μ l of a 0.05% saponin solution for 20 minutes. Following this, 50 μ l of a 0.5 mg/ml MTT solution was added to each well, and the plate was incubated at room temperature for 60 minutes at 37°C to allow for formazan formation. The formazan was then solubilized using isopropanol. Absorbance (optical density) was measured at dual wavelengths of 595 and 630 nm using an ELISA reader. The absorbance of formazan is directly proportional to the number of viable bacteria present. The percentage of bacteria killed in each well was calculated using the appropriate formula.

Percentage (%) of bacteria killed = $[1 - (\text{OD sample} - \text{OD 90\% killing}) / (\text{OD 0\% killing} - \text{OD 90\% killing})] \times 90\%$. The data were presented in percentage with Mean \pm SD.

2.11. In vitro phagocytic assay [nitrobluetetrazolium(NBT) reduction test]

To assess the functional capabilities of activated phagocytes, the Nitro Blue Tetrazolium (NBT) reduction assay is commonly employed. This technique serves as a dependable indicator of oxidative burst activity, as NBT is converted to insoluble formazan, offering a quantitative assessment of phagocytic activation. The phagocytic assay was conducted in accordance with the protocol established by Rainard.^[40] In brief, 100 μ l of RBMCs at a concentration of 5×10^6 cells per well were obtained from various treatment groups in a 96-well plate. Following this, 33.33 μ l of a live *S. aureus* suspension (3×10^8 CFU/ml) was added, maintaining a bacteria-to-macrophage ratio of 10:1, along with 20 μ l of nitrobluetetrazolium (NBT) solution at a concentration of 1.5 mg/ml. The mixture was incubated for an additional 60 minutes at 37°C. After incubation, the supernatant was

removed, and the adherent macrophages were washed with DMEM medium. The cells were allowed to air-dry before the addition of 120 μ l of 2M potassium hydroxide (KOH) and 140 μ l of DMSO to each well. The absorbance of the resulting turquoise blue solution was then measured at 570 nm using a plate reader. The percentage of NBT reduction, which reflects phagocytic activity, was calculated using the following equation:

Phagocytic index = $(OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{control}}) / OD_{\text{control}} \times 100$.^[41] The data (phagocytic index) were presented as Mean \pm SD.

2.12. Western blot analysis was conducted to examine the expression levels of various proteins in both undifferentiated and differentiated RBMCs

Lysate proteins from various groups were prepared using RIPA Lysis buffer, which consists of 20 mM TrisHCl, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% Triton X-100, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS, and 1 mM PMSF. Following this, the samples underwent centrifugation at 10,000 rpm to obtain a cell-free lysate, and the protein concentration of each lysate was standardized using the Lowry method.^[42] A total of 10 μ g of the protein samples were then subjected to separation on a 10% SDS-polyacrylamide gel, after which they were transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane. To prevent non-specific binding, the membrane was blocked with Tris-buffered saline containing Tween-20 (TBST) (20 mM Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 0.1% Tween 20) containing 5% bovine serum albumin (BSA). The membranes were washed thrice in TBST and probed overnight at 4 °C with the following primary antibodies separately: IL-1 β antibody (Cat No: 26048-1-AP; Proteintech, 1:100), IL-1 Receptor antibody (Cat No: orb6227; Biorbyt Ltd, 1:100), TNF- α antibody (Cat No: 17590-1-AP; Proteintech, 1:100), IL-10 antibody (Cat No: orb22682, Biorbyt 1:100), mTOR antibody (Cat No: 66888-I-Ig; Proteintech, 1:100), TGF- β 1 antibody (Cat No: 21898-1-AP; Proteintech, 1:100), STAT5 antibody (Cat No: 66427-1-Ig; Proteintech, 1:100), BCL2 antibody (Cat No: ab692; Abcam, 1:100) and LC3 antibody (Cat No: orb33336; Biorbyt, 1:100). The blots underwent three washes in TBST and were subsequently incubated with suitable horse radish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated secondary antibodies at a dilution of 1:5000 for two hours at room temperature. Detection of the antigen was achieved using the SuperSignal chemiluminescent substrate (SuperSignal West Pico Chemiluminescent Substrate; Thermo Scientific), and visualization was performed by exposing X-Omat BT films (Kodak). Beta-tubulin (Catalog No: orb 11537, Biorbyt Ltd, at a dilution of 1:100) served as the loading control to confirm that equal protein amounts were loaded across the gel lanes. Densitometric data were

analyzed using ImageJ software, and the fold increase measurements were reported as arbitrary units normalized to the expression of β -tubulin.

2.13. Statistical analysis

The isolated RBMCs from three mice in each group were combined to achieve a target cell concentration of 5×10^6 cells/ml. This systematic approach involved conducting experiments in triplicate to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to identify significant differences between the groups, with a significance threshold set at a p-value of less than 0.05. The primary aim of our current study is to evaluate the functional responses of RBMCs across various experimental groups. Consequently, a minimum concentration of 5×10^6 cells/ml was necessary, which required pooling the isolated RBMCs from three mice within each respective group. Each experimental set was repeated three times (biological replicates), thus precluding the possibility of analyzing specific parameters from individual mice. Statistical analysis was performed on the triplicate data set using one-way ANOVA, with group comparisons based on the means of pooled cell populations for each group, maintaining a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Impact of TLR4 or IFN γ Neutralization with Exogenous IL-10 on H₂O₂ Release by Resident Bone Marrow Cells in LPS-stimulated Mice Following 3 Days of Culture

Resident bone marrow cells (RBMCs) were isolated from various experimental groups of mice, as described in the Methods section, and subsequently stimulated *in vitro* with LPS, RANKL, and M-CSF for 3 days. Following incubation, the cells were harvested, and H₂O₂ release was quantified using a spectrophotometric assay based on horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-mediated oxidation of phenol red. The results demonstrated a significant increase in H₂O₂ release in the RBMCs of the LPS-challenged group compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). Notably, RBMCs obtained from mice pre-treated with both TLR4-neutralizing antibody (TLR4Ab) and IFN γ -neutralizing antibody (IFN γ Ab) prior to LPS administration exhibited a reduced level of H₂O₂ release relative to the LPS-only group. Furthermore, RBMCs from group that received additional exogenous IL-10 supplementation alongside TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab prior to LPS exposure displayed an even greater reduction in H₂O₂ levels compared to those that did not receive IL-10 post-treatment. In contrast, RBMCs isolated from mice that received IL-10 supplementation following LPS challenge alone

exhibited an increased H₂O₂ release compared to both the dual antibody-treated group and the IL-10 co-treatment group. [Figure2].

Figure 2: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on H₂O₂ production in differentiated RBMCs. RBMCs were stimulated in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days to induce differentiation.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed in $\mu\text{M}/10^6$ cells as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.2. Impact of TLR4 or IFN γ Neutralization with Exogenous IL-10 on NO Release by Resident Bone Marrow Cells in LPS-stimulated Mice Following 3 Days of Culture

Bone marrow cells were isolated from various experimental groups, and the nitric oxide (NO) released into the medium was quantified using the Griess Assay. The results indicated that

the NO release from cells in the LPS-challenged group was significantly greater than that of the control group ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, RBMCs obtained from mice that were pre-treated with TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab prior to LPS challenge exhibited a reduced NO release compared to those from the LPS-only challenged group. Additionally, the NO levels in RBMCs from mice subjected to TLR4 and IFN γ blockade, followed by LPS and subsequent IL-10 treatment, were markedly lower than those in RBMCs from mice that did not receive post-treatment. Furthermore, RBMCs from mice treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab without the addition of exogenous IL-10 also demonstrated reduced NO levels in the presence of LPS. Conversely, RBMCs from mice that received IL-10 supplementation after the LPS challenge showed a lower NO release compared to those from the LPS-challenged group that did not receive any treatment ($p < 0.05$). [Figure3].

Figure 3: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on NO production in differentiated RBMCs. RBMCs were stimulated in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days to induce differentiation.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed in $\mu\text{M}/10^6$ cells as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group.

3.3. Impact of TLR4 or IFN γ Neutralization with Exogenous IL-10 on Superoxide anion Release by Resident Bone Marrow Cells in LPS-stimulated Mice Following 3 Days of Culture

In comparison to the control macrophages, the release of Superoxide anion was significantly elevated in the LPS-challenged cells ($p < 0.05$), as illustrated in **Figure 4**. Macrophages that were pre-treated with TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab prior to LPS exposure exhibited the lower levels of Superoxide anion production when compared to those stimulated with LPS. Additionally, the dual antibody treatment before LPS administration resulted in a slight increase in superoxide release. Moreover, RBMCs from mice treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, along with exogenous IL-10, displayed the most significant reduction in superoxide levels in the presence of LPS. In contrast, RBMCs from mice that received both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab with IL-10 supplementation, but without LPS, showed an elevated level of superoxide release.

Figure 4: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on Superoxide anion production in differentiated RBMCs. RBMCs were stimulated in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days to induce differentiation.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed in $\mu\text{M}/10^6$ cells as mean \pm SD which are

significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.4. The use of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab in conjunction with exogenous IL-10 resulted in an increase in lysozyme enzyme activity in both undifferentiated RBMCs and those cultured for 3 days

Lysozyme enzyme levels were assessed in both undifferentiated and cultured cells, revealing comparable results under both conditions. As illustrated in **Figure 5A**, lysozyme activity significantly decreased in LPS-stimulated macrophages compared to control macrophages. However, enzyme activity was restored in the group treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, along with IL-10 supplementation in the presence of LPS. A similar recovery was observed in groups pretreated with either TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab, or both, in conjunction with LPS. Conversely, the group receiving both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab with IL-10 supplementation, but without LPS, exhibited a reduced level of lysozyme activity.

A similar pattern was observed in differentiated cells [**Figure 5B**], with the notable distinction that the lysozyme activity in the comprehensive treatment group was more effectively restored compared to the undifferentiated condition.

Figure 5: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on Lysozyme enzyme activity assay in RBMCs. (A)

Lysozyme enzyme activity assay was done from the cell free lysate of RBMCs which were not stimulated with in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days. (B) Lysozyme enzyme activity assay was done from the cell free lysate of RBMCs which were stimulated with in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in both presence and absence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed in units/ μ g of protein as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.5. The combined use of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab along with exogenous IL-10 increases the overall phagocytic activity (Membrane Fluidity) of RBMCs (undifferentiated)

Table 1: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on the membrane fluidity in undifferentiated RBMCs. RBMCs which were not with stimulated in-vitro RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS.

Name of the group	Total Phagocytic activity (OD at 490 nm) (Mean \pm SD)
Control	0.585 \pm 0.025
LPS	0.2655 \pm 0.0605*
TLR4Ab + LPS	0.693 \pm 0.272 [#]
IFN γ Ab + LPS	0.6605 \pm 0.0035 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS	0.5105 \pm 0.0205 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	0.5805 \pm 0.1145 ^{#@}
LPS + IL10	0.3025 \pm 0.1905
TLR4Ab + LPS + IL10	0.4815 \pm 0.0625 [#]
IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	0.461 \pm 0.046 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + IL10	0.3235 \pm 0.0165 [#]

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in absence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Where the data directly represented as OD value which was taken at 490nm. Higher the OD value represent higher membrane fluidity rate. From here the total phagocytic activity of RBMCs can be observed. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant

difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group and ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group.

Table 1 illustrates the overall phagocytic activity of the cells (undifferentiated), indicating a notable reduction in phagocytic activity in the group challenged solely with LPS compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). This activity was restored following the administration of TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab prior to LPS exposure. Notably, the recovery rate was significantly greater in the group receiving comprehensive treatment. Furthermore, the group that was pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, along with exogenous IL-10 (without LPS), exhibited a higher phagocytic index compared to the group exposed only to LPS.

3.6. The combined use of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab along with exogenous IL-10 increases the overall bactericidal activity (% of bacterial killing) of RBMCs (undifferentiated)

Table 2 illustrates the percentage of bacteria eliminated by the undifferentiated cells, revealing a significant decrease in bacterial killing in the group exposed exclusively to LPS when compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). The bacterial killing percentage was restored after administering TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab prior to LPS exposure. Remarkably, the highest percentage was observed in the group that received TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, along with exogenous IL-10 (with LPS), in comparison to all other groups challenged with LPS. Additionally, the group pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, along with exogenous IL-10 (without LPS), demonstrated a higher percentage of bacterial killing than the group that was solely exposed to LPS.

Table 2: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on the ability of total bacteria killed (in %) in undifferentiated RBMCs. RBMCs which were not with stimulated in-vitro RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS.

Name of the group	% of bacteria killed (Mean \pm SD)
Control	105.950 \pm 15.756
LPS	4.069 \pm 3.478*
TLR4Ab + LPS	12.054 \pm 2.570
IFN γ Ab + LPS	15.706 \pm 4.093
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS	5.168 \pm 0.443
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	37.839 \pm 6.485 ^{#&\$@+}
LPS + IL10	14.201 \pm 0.701 [#]
TLR4Ab + LPS + IL10	9.765 \pm 0.475

IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	11.434 \pm 9.662
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + IL10	87.414 \pm 14.060 [#]

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in absence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Where the result represented as the % of bacteria killed by the macrophages. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.7. The combined use of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab along with exogenous IL-10 increases the overall % of phagocytic index (NBT Reduction) of RBMCs(undifferentiated)

Table 3: Effects of endogenous TLR4 and IFN γ blockade prior to LPS stimulation, combined with exogenous IL-10, on the % of phagocytic index in undifferentiated RBMCs. RBMCs which were not with stimulated in-vitro RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS.

Name of the group	% of Phagocytic index (Mean \pm SD)
Control	650.195 \pm 115.713
LPS	62.774 \pm 6.383*
TLR4Ab + LPS	107.420 \pm 60.803
IFN γ Ab + LPS	210.786 \pm 30.335 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS	144.315 \pm 5.217 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	418.628 \pm 143.440 ^{#&+}
LPS + IL10	198.879 \pm 68.038 [#]
TLR4Ab + LPS + IL10	184.568 \pm 11.671 [#]
IFN γ Ab + LPS + IL10	320.019 \pm 68.617 [#]
TLR4Ab + IFN γ Ab + IL10	324.176 \pm 148.236 [#]

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in absence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Where the result represented as the % of phagocytic index of the macrophages. It means higher the phagocytic index macrophages have the ability to engulf antigen. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group and ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

The overall percentage of the phagocytic index showed a significant reduction in the group challenged solely with LPS when compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, the index was elevated in the groups pre-treated with either TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab compared to the LPS group. However, the results were even more pronounced in the groups that received IL-10 treatment prior to the LPS challenge. The highest phagocytic index was recorded in the comprehensive treatment group (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10)[**Table 3**].

3.8. Expression of IL-1 β , IL-1R, TNF α , IL-10, mTOR via western blot in presence of in-vitro culture of RBMCs with M-CSF and RANK for 3 days, i.e. from differentiated RBMCs

IL-1 β expression was notably higher in the LPS challenged group in comparison to that from the control and other groups. TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab pretreated group that received LPS challenge subsequently showed a diminished level of IL-1 β expression. The group which was pretreated with dual antibody prior to exogenous IL-10 post-treatment (with LPS) showed the lowest level of expression ($p < 0.05$)[**Figure 6A**].

In **Figure 6B**, reveals a substantial decrease in IL-1R expression within the LPS (only) challenged group, whereas an augmented expression was observed in the all-encompassing treatment group (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10). The single or dual antibody treated group with LPS challenged showed a higher level of expression ($p < 0.05$).

In **Figure 6C**, The TNF α expression was observed to be the maximum in the RBMCs of LPS challenged group, and in comparison, to that TNF α showed down regulated expression in the cells from the group of mice that were treated with TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab prior to LPS challenge and exogenous IL-10. Similarly, the group pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab prior to LPS challenge along with exogenous IL-10 supplementation has shown the highest diminished level of TNF α expression in their RBMCs ($p < 0.05$).

The IL-10 expression was downregulated in the RBMCs of only LPS challenged group as compared to other groups ($p < 0.05$). It showed a significantly upregulated in TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab or dual antibody (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab) treated group with LPS challenged. Specially, the LPS challenged groups with both antibodies treated along with IL-10 supplementation has shown even more elevated expression [**Figure 6D**].

mTOR expression was found to be the maximum in the LPS challenged group. The expression was higher in the RBMCs of the groups that received pretreatment with either

IFN γ Ab or TLR4Ab or both prior to LPS challenge but were not supplemented with IL-10, relative to the groups which were supplemented with that IL-10 ($p < 0.05$). Also, the group that received pretreatment with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab with IL-10 supplementation has shown diminished expression of mTOR [Figure 6E].

Figure 6: Western blot analyses of (A) IL-1 β , (B) IL-1R, (C) TNF α , (D) IL-10, (E) mTOR from resident bone marrow macrophages which were stimulated in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.9. Expression of TGF β 1, STAT5, Bcl2 and LC3 via western blot in presence of in-vitro culture of RBMCs with M-CSF and RANK for 3 days, i.e. from differentiated RBMCs

In **Figure 7A**, the expression of TGF β 1 was decreased in the RBMCs of only LPS administrated group. The treatment groups, and notably the combination group (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10), exhibited an increased in TGF β 1 expression ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, STAT5 expression, as depicted in **Figure 7B**, was remarkably higher in the RBMCs recovered from only LPS administered mice as opposed to that of the lysate from cells of the control group ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, RBMCs of TLR4 or IFN γ or both (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab) neutralized LPS challenged group has shown notable decrease in STAT5 expression as compared to the group with only LPS challenge. Similarly, the LPS challenged groups with prior neutralization of TLR4 or IFN γ or both along with IL-10 supplementation has shown even more diminished expression of STAT5 than that in the groups without the additional IL-10 post-treatment.

Bcl2 expression was found to be higher in the RBMCs of LPS challenged group when compared to control group, but the expression was lower when compared to all-inclusive treatment group ($p < 0.05$). The RBMCs isolated from the TLR4 pretreated group with IL-10 supplementation (LPS challenged) are hardly showing any difference in Bcl2 expression relative to the group that lacked that IL-10 supplementation. However, the group with either TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab pretreatment followed by LPS challenge has shown upregulation of Bcl2 expression in their RBMCs, relative to the group with only LPS challenge. Furthermore, the IFN γ Ab pretreated group with IL-10 treatment (LPS challenged) was also showing increased Bcl2 expression relative to the group that lacked that IL-10 treatment. There was an increase in the all-inclusive treatment group (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10) [**Figure 7C**].

The LPS (only) challenged group shows the greatest amount of upregulation in LC3 expression in their RBMCs. Conversely, the control group shows the lowest amount of LC3 level. Exogenous IL-10 supplementation has been seen to downregulate the LC3 expression in the group that was pretreated with TLR4Ab or IFN γ Ab or both and subsequently challenged with LPS, whereas the similar group without the post treatment has greater expression of LC3. Similarly, IL-10 supplementation in group with LPS challenge has shown a downregulated expression of LC3 in comparison with LPS alone challenged group ($p < 0.05$) [**Figure 7D**].

Figure 7: Western blot analyses of (A)TGFβ1, (B)STAT5, (C)BCL2, (D)LC3 from resident bone marrow macrophages which were stimulated in-vitro with RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.10. Expression of IL-1 β , IL-1R, TNF α , IL-10, mTOR via western blot in absence of in-vitro culture of RBMCs with M-CSF and RANK, i.e. from undifferentiated RBMCs

It was observed that the expression of IL-1 β was more in the RBMC of LPS challenged group than in the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, RBMC that were recovered from mice pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, exhibited reduced expression of IL-1 β in comparison to RBMCs of the LPS challenged group. In contrast, RBMCs isolated from mice that were pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS administration and also supplemented with IL-10 had diminished expression of IL-1 β than the RBMCs of TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS group [that had not received exogenous IL-10] [Figure 8A].

The **Figure 8B**, reveals a substantial increase in IL-1R expression within the LPS group as compared to control ($p < 0.05$), whereas an augmented expression was observed in the group which pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, and supplemented with IL-10. This could reflect a feedback inhibition loop where the presence of inflammatory stimuli (LPS) suppresses IL-1R, or alternatively, the combined treatment modulates the immune response to upregulate IL-1R expression.

The expression of TNF α [Figure 8C], with the LPS group showing higher levels than the control ($p < 0.05$), and the mice pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, and supplemented with IL-10 presented the lowest expression.

The IL-10 expression [**Figure 8D**], follows a opposite trend, with the LPS group showing lower levels than the control ($p < 0.05$), and the TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group presenting the highest expression.

The expression of mTOR was more in the RBMCs of LPS challenged group than in the control group ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, RBMCs from mice pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, depicted reduced expression of mTOR in comparison to RBMCs of the LPS challenged group. Conversely, RBMCs isolated from mice that were pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS administration and also supplemented with IL-10 had diminished expression of mTOR than the RBMCs of TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS group [that had not received exogenous IL-10]. To the contrary, the expression of mTOR was found to be notably reduced in the RBMCs of mice treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab plus supplemented with exogenous IL-10 [No LPS], than the mTOR expression in RBMCs treated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab as well as post IL-10 treatment [+LPS] [**Figure 8E**].

Figure 8: Western blot analyses of (A) IL-1 β , (B) IL-1R, (C) TNF α , (D) IL-10, (E) mTOR from resident bone marrow macrophages which were remain unstimulated with in-vitro RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

3.11. Expression of TGF β 1, STAT5, BCL2 and LC3 via western blot in absence of in-vitro culture of RBMCs with M-CSF and RANK for 3 days, i.e. from undifferentiated RBMCs

The highest downregulation of TGF β 1 [Figure 9A] was observed in the LPS group. However, the pretreatment with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS stimulation with exogenous IL-10 showed upregulation of TGF β 1, but the expression was found to be significantly reduced in the group with pretreated with only LPS challenge with exogenous IL-10 ($p < 0.05$).

The pattern of upregulation in only LPS challenged group [Figure 9B] was also observed in the expression of STAT5, where the RBMCs retrieved from mice pretreated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, showed reduced STAT5 expression, relative to RBMCs of the LPS challenged group. The expression combined treatment group (TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10) again exhibits the most significant reduction ($p < 0.05$).

The RBMCs of mice challenged with LPS exhibited significantly higher BC12 expression [Figure 9C] compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, RBMCs from mice pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge showed induction of BC12 expression relative to the LPS challenged group. Interestingly, RBMCs from mice pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge and also supplemented with IL-10, displayed significantly higher BC12 expression compared to those treated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab prior to LPS challenge (which had not received exogenous IL-10). Conversely, RBMCs from mice treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab followed by IL-10 supplementation (without LPS) exhibited markedly higher BC12 expression than the LPS challenged group. As well as the all-inclusive treatment group showed the highest level of BC12 expression.

In Figure 9D, LC3 expression, mice challenged with LPS, was higher compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). The mice pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, showed a decrease in LC3 expression compared to the mice that were LPS challenged. RBMCs from mice pretreated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab before LPS challenge, and supplemented with IL-10, exhibited further diminished LC3 expression compared to those treated with TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab prior to LPS challenge (without IL-10). The RBMCs from mice treated with both TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab followed by IL-10 supplementation (without LPS) displayed lower LC3 expression than the TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group.

Figure 9: Western blot analyses of (A)TGFβ1, (B)STAT5, (C)BCl2, (D) LC3 from resident bone marrow macrophages which were remain unstimulated with in-vitro RANKL, M-CSF, and LPS for 3 days.

The experiments were conducted in mice from different experimental groups in presence of in-vitro RANKL and M-CSF with LPS stimulation. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD which are significant at the level of $p < 0.05$. ‘*’ denoted significant difference in comparison to control group, ‘#’ indicates significant difference compared to LPS group, ‘&’ indicates significant difference in comparison to TLR4Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘\$’ denoted significant difference compared to IFN- γ Ab+LPS+IL-10 group, ‘@’ showed significant difference compared to TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 group. ‘+’ indicates significant difference in comparison to LPS+IL-10 group.

4. DISCUSSION

Bone loss is a hallmark of inflammatory osteolytic lesions and is predominantly driven by an abnormal increase in osteoclast differentiation and activity. Under physiological conditions, bone remodeling is a tightly coupled and well-coordinated process between osteoblasts and osteoclasts that ensures the maintenance of skeletal tissue integrity. However, in certain inflammatory disorders, such as LPS induced osteoclastogenesis, this balance is disrupted. The resulting imbalance in the activity of bone cells, particularly through enhanced osteoclast differentiation and activity, leads to progressive bone loss and skeletal deterioration.^[43] In this study, we showed that in vivo bone resorption induced by LPS, when further stimulated with

RANKL and M-CSF, is downregulated by TLR4 and IFN γ antibodies in the presence of exogenous IL-10. Furthermore, we have shown that treatment of mice with TLR4 and IFN γ antibody and exogenous IL-10 in a LPS induced bone damage model could modulate BC12 and LC3 expression in RANKL/M-CSF plus LPS stimulated resident bone marrow cells indicating to bone resorption. Additionally, these factors exhibited contrasting effects in the interaction between LC3 and BC12. In our earlier research, we determined that the mechanism responsible for this inhibitory effect involved the direct suppression of the RANKL/TLR4/NF- κ B/STAT3 signaling pathway. This suppression facilitates the nuclear translocation of NF- κ B p65, leading to the downregulation of key pro-inflammatory molecules, including SOCS3, iNOS and COX2 which in turn regulates the differentiation and fusion of osteoclasts.^[15]

Autophagy plays a fundamental role in regulating various cellular processes, including proliferation, differentiation, and survival, and primarily functions as an adaptive mechanism to maintain homeostasis within organisms.^[44] Emerging research indicates that specific environmental conditions, such as nutrient deprivation and high-glucose-induced inflammation, can modulate autophagic activity in pre-osteoclasts. These alterations in autophagy significantly influence osteoclastogenesis, thereby contributing to pathological changes in bone metabolism and skeletal disorders.^[45] Our research demonstrates that bone inflammation induced by LPS affects the expression of autophagic markers in resident bone marrow macrophages. Importantly, autophagy can be pharmacologically influenced by certain compounds. For example, inhibitors of the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR), which typically inhibit autophagy, have been found to increase autophagic activity, underscoring their potential therapeutic role in regulating this process.^[46] Research indicates that in C57BL/6J mice, cellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) induced by LPS facilitate the nuclear translocation of p65. This observation implies that the influence of LPS on NF- κ B activation in osteoclasts is regulated by the ROS/PP2A/IKK α / β /p65 signaling pathway.^[47] Additionally, mTOR is exacerbated by the accumulation of ROS.^[48] In our investigation, we also observed that LPS elevated ROS levels in cultured cells over several days; however, following treatment, there was a significant decrease in ROS levels, which correspondingly led to a reduction in mTOR expression.

Lysozyme, a well-characterized antibacterial protein, plays a crucial role in innate immunity by hydrolyzing bacterial cell walls. It is widely distributed across various biological fluids

and tissues, including tears, saliva, respiratory secretions, and polymorphonuclear leukocytes.^[49] In addition to its bacteriolytic function, lysozyme has been shown to modulate immune responses. Previous studies have demonstrated its ability to enhance antibody production in lymphocytes and augment antibacterial and immunostimulatory activities, particularly following heat treatment.^[50] Notably, research by Tagashira et al. has revealed that lysozyme inhibits the phosphorylation of c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), thereby suppressing the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokine genes in hyperinflammatory macrophages.^[51] These findings suggest that lysozyme exerts immunoregulatory effects through multiple molecular mechanisms *in vitro*. Building upon these findings, our previous work demonstrated a reduced expression of the STAT1 protein following lysozyme activation, which was associated with decreased JNK phosphorylation under comprehensive treatment conditions. In the present study, we observed that LPS effectively downregulated lysozyme expression under both cultured and uncultured conditions, contributing to an inflammatory state. However, therapeutic intervention was able to mitigate this effect, preserving lysozyme levels and promoting its upregulation, thereby suggesting a protective role against LPS-induced suppression.

Macrophages are key players in innate immunity, exhibiting a strong phagocytic capacity essential for microbial clearance and immune homeostasis. Efficient phagocytosis of pathogens and particles is a fundamental function of macrophages, and alterations in this process can significantly impact immune responses. Previous research by Oppong-Nonterah et al. in 2019 demonstrated that exposure to LPS during bone marrow-derived macrophage differentiation led to a reduction in phagocytic activity, suggesting a potential impairment in immune function due to TLR activation.^[52] The initial step of phagocytosis involves antigen engulfment, a process that requires increased membrane fluidity and the activation of specific membrane-associated proteins. Notably, there is a well-established correlation between phagocytic efficiency and membrane fluidity.^[53] In our study, we observed a significant enhancement in phagocytosis across all-inclusive treatment groups. However, this effect was completely abolished upon LPS exposure, further reinforcing the inhibitory impact of LPS on macrophage phagocytic function. Our findings suggest that the combination of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab, in conjunction with exogenous IL-10, enhanced membrane fluidity, thereby increasing the capacity for antigen engulfment.

The improvement of membrane fluidity enhanced the ability of macrophages to clear bacteria. This finding is corroborated by our bactericidal activity assay, which revealed a significantly reduced percentage of bacterial killing in the group stimulated with LPS. Conversely, the bactericidal effectiveness of macrophages was significantly enhanced when treated with a combination of dual antibodies (TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab) along with exogenous IL-10. These results indicate that the modulation of membrane dynamics is essential for optimizing the antimicrobial functions of macrophages, especially in inflammatory conditions where LPS negatively affects phagocytic and bactericidal activities. The phagocytic index was assessed using the NBT assay, which measures macrophage oxidative burst activity. During phagocytosis, macrophages generate ROS, reducing yellow NBT dye into insoluble blue formazan. The intensity of formazan deposition correlates with macrophage phagocytic function.^[54] The formazan deposits can be quantified using spectrophotometry after solubilization in an organic solvent like dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), providing an objective measure of macrophage activation and bactericidal potential. We observed the similar results where total phagocytic activity reduced by the LPS was further recovered in treatment group.

To investigate the cellular signaling pathways involved in inflammation and autophagy, protein expression was assessed using Western blot analysis. IL-1 β , a key pro-inflammatory cytokine, is predominantly produced by dendritic cells, monocytes, T cells, and macrophages.^[55] Previous studies have reported that under inflammatory conditions, starved macrophages secrete IL-1 β in an autophagy-dependent manner.^[56] However, the precise mechanism by which IL-1 β is secreted rather than degraded within autophagic organelles remains unclear. In our study, IL-1 β secretion was evaluated in both differentiated and undifferentiated RBMCs by LPS stimulation. The results demonstrated that LPS stimulation led to the highest levels of IL-1 β secretion, which in turn activated autophagic processes. However, when TLR4 and IFN γ were blocked using their respective antibodies, LPS was unable to induce IL-1 β secretion. This inhibition resulted in the downregulation of the entire inflammatory and autophagic signaling cascade.

During inflammatory conditions, mature IL-1 β primarily binds to interleukin-1 receptor type I (IL-1RI), leading to the formation of a heterodimeric receptor complex. The Toll/interleukin-1 receptor (TIR) domain of the receptor subsequently recruits myeloid differentiation primary response 88 (MyD88), initiating a signaling cascade. This process involves the phosphorylation of IL-1 receptor-associated kinases (IRAKs) and inhibitor of

NF- κ B kinase β (IKK β), ultimately resulting in nuclear signaling and inflammatory gene expression. IL-1 β also interacts with interleukin-1 receptor type II (IL-1RII), which lacks a cytoplasmic signaling domain and therefore does not transduce signals.^[57] Notably we found that under inflammatory conditions, receptor complex formation with IL-1 β was associated with reduced expression of IL-1RI in the LPS group. However, following therapeutic intervention, IL-1 β production was significantly reduced, leading to decreased heterodimer formation and increased IL-1RI expression in the comprehensive treatment group.

TNF α has been shown to play a significant role in bone resorption linked to inflammatory bone diseases.^[58] It affects the differentiation of osteoclast precursors and their resorptive activity through several mechanisms, including the stimulation of RANKL and M-CSF expression in osteogenic cells, which in turn facilitates the differentiation and function of osteoclasts.^[59] Our investigation revealed that in both undifferentiated and differentiated RBMCs, TNF- α expression was elevated in the LPS-stimulated group, which further amplified the RANKL-mediated inflammatory signaling pathway. This process was inhibited by the application of TLR4 and IFN γ antibodies in conjunction with IL-10 treatment.

IL-10 is a well-established anti-inflammatory cytokine that plays a crucial role in protecting mice against the lethal effects of LPS by suppressing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Previous studies have demonstrated that LPS stimulation induces IL-10 production as early as 1.5 hours post-exposure; however, its expression diminishes after 6 to 12 hours.^[60] Upon binding to its receptor, IL-10 triggers the activation of Janus kinase 1 (Jak1) and tyrosine kinase 2 (Tyk2), leading to the phosphorylation of signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3). Gene-targeted mouse models have highlighted the essential role of Jak1 and STAT3 in IL-10-mediated signaling.^[61] Our previous research identified a biphasic function of STAT3, where its upregulation in the presence of IL-10 contributed to its anti-inflammatory properties. In the current study, we observed a significant reduction in IL-10 levels in the LPS-treated group, whereas IL-10 expression was markedly enhanced under treatment conditions. Consequently, the overall circulating concentrations of M-CSF and RANKL were significantly attenuated, further reinforcing the immunomodulatory role of IL-10 in LPS induced inflammation.

LPS, upon interacting with TLR4, increases the levels of ROS within cells. Research has shown that ROS play a crucial role in modulating the phosphorylation of AKT signalling,^[62] which subsequently activates PI3K/AKT, leading to the activation of mTOR and the

regulation of the inflammatory response.^[63] In our study, mTOR levels were found to be elevated in inflammatory conditions, which in turn promotes the production of additional pro-inflammatory cytokines. However, treatment resulted in a reduction of mTOR levels and a suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokine production. mTOR is also connected to TGF β , a multifunctional cytokine that influences various cellular processes such as activation, proliferation, differentiation, migration, and apoptosis.^[64,65,66] Previous research has demonstrated that TGF β enhances macrophage glycolysis via an mTOR-MYC dependent pathway following the activation of the TLR pathway. Furthermore, TGF β has been shown to decrease the production of inflammatory cytokines in macrophages by inhibiting pro-inflammatory transcription factors, including NF- κ B and STAT.^[67] Additionally, TGF β plays a role in the development and functionality of microglia and alveolar macrophages.^[68] In our studies involving bone marrow-derived macrophages, we observed that TGF β levels were suppressed under inflammatory conditions, while an increase was noted following the TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 treatment. This suggests that our intervention effectively reduced the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines associated with bone resorption.

LPS triggered the activation of STAT5 in human monocytes, with this activation occurring indirectly through the granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF) released by LPS-activated monocytes. However, the activation of STAT5 was inhibited by IL-10, which suppressed GM-CSF production.^[69] This suggests that STAT5 plays a pro-inflammatory role in human monocytes. Our experiments also demonstrated that LPS stimulation led to an upregulation of STAT5. Furthermore, it was experimentally established that IL-7 can directly activate STAT5 to promote the formation of osteoclast cells in response to RANKL stimulation.^[18] We observed that treatment resulted in a reduction of STAT5 expression, thereby regulating the bone resorption process.

The anti-apoptotic protein Bcl2 plays a crucial role in inhibiting apoptosis by blocking the release of cytochrome c from mitochondria. While numerous studies have highlighted the significance of Bcl2 in preserving skeletal structure, the specific cellular and molecular processes involved remain unclear.^[70,71] In Bcl2 transgenic mice, an increase in bone volume was observed at 6 weeks of age, but this was not the case at 10 weeks when compared to wild-type mice. Although the number of osteoblasts and osteocytes rose, both osteoid thickness and the rate of bone formation decreased in Bcl2 transgenic mice exhibiting high expression levels at 10 weeks.^[72] Various studies have shown that Bcl2 knockout mice

exhibit greater bone activity. However, our research unexpectedly revealed that elevated BCL2 expression contributes to the recovery of bone mass in Swiss albino mice. Further investigation is required to elucidate the underlying mechanisms. This phenomenon occurs may be because, under treatment conditions, the anti-apoptotic function of BCL2 protects against cell death, while reduced levels of LC3 lead to diminished autophagy. These two interactions promote macrophage survival and decrease the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines.

Numerous studies have highlighted the critical role of autophagy in the differentiation and functionality of osteoclasts.^[73] It has been observed that the expression of autophagy-related proteins rises during the process of osteoclast differentiation. A prior investigation involving 8-week-old male C57BL6/J mice revealed an increase in the LC3-II form during RANKL-induced osteoclastogenesis.^[74] Consistent with earlier findings, the current study also identified an elevation of LC3 under LPS-stimulated conditions, indicating a positive correlation with autophagy in relation to bone resorption. This expression was reduced when treated with antibodies [Figure 10].

Figure 10: Possible signaling pathway of RBMCs which were stimulated by RANKL+M-CSF+LPS for 3 days in-vitro.

(A) Schematic representation of the molecular mechanisms linking LPS, RANKL, and M-CSF signaling to osteoclastogenesis via pro-inflammatory and autophagy pathways. LPS binding to TLR4 activates pro-inflammatory signaling through TRAF6, leading to increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and mTOR upregulation, which in turn enhances pro-inflammatory cytokine expression. TRAF6 also upregulates LC3, a key autophagy regulator, promoting osteoclastogenesis. Under inflammatory conditions, IFN γ further amplifies the TRAF6-mediated pathway. Additionally, LPS suppresses TGF β , a potent anti-inflammatory marker, reducing its inhibitory effect on inflammation. RANKL and M-CSF binding to their respective receptors further stimulate inflammatory signaling, with RANKL upregulating IL-7, activating STAT5, and reducing BCL2 levels. Pro-inflammatory cytokines, including M-CSF, TNF α , and IL-1 β , contribute to the process, ultimately enhancing autophagy and promoting osteoclast-mediated bone resorption.

(B) Schematic representation of the suppressed inflammatory and autophagy pathways following treatment with TLR4Ab, IFN γ Ab, and IL-10. Blocking TLR4 with TLR4Ab prevents LPS entry, leading to reduced TRAF6 expression and diminished cellular ROS levels. This allows TGF β to exert its anti-inflammatory effects against pro-inflammatory cytokines. Additionally, IFN γ Ab blocks IFN γ signaling, preventing further activation of inflammatory pathways. Despite the presence of RANKL and M-CSF, their signaling alone is insufficient to induce autophagy. IL-10 further enhances the anti-inflammatory response, collectively inhibiting LPS-mediated autophagy and downregulating osteoclast-mediated bone resorption.

Our study demonstrates that elevated levels of BCL2 correlate with LC3 expression, effectively downregulating bone resorption in Swiss albino mice. Furthermore, treatment with TLR4Ab+IFN γ Ab+IL-10 successfully restores the phagocytic activity of macrophages while simultaneously suppressing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. These findings highlight a potential therapeutic strategy for mitigating bone loss associated with LPS-induced inflammation by modulating apoptotic and autophagic pathways [**Figure 11**].

Figure 11: Possible signaling pathway of RBMCs which were remain unstimulated by RANKL+M-CSF+LPS for 3 days.

(A) Schematic representation of the autophagic response in RBMCs exposed to LPS without in vitro RANKL and M-CSF stimulation. LPS alone triggers the inflammatory signaling cascade (detailed in Figure 10A), leading to autophagy induction. In the absence of in-vitro RANKL stimulation, the pro-inflammatory response may drive endogenous RANKL production, contributing to BCL2 downregulation and IL-7-mediated STAT5 upregulation. This mechanism highlights the ability of LPS to independently induce autophagy through inflammatory signaling pathways.

(B) Schematic representation of the inhibitory effects of antibodies and IL-10 on LPS-induced inflammation and autophagy. Antibodies effectively block LPS binding sites, significantly reducing pro-inflammatory signaling and autophagy induction. IL-10 serves as a key anti-inflammatory mediator, directly suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokine production. This inhibition prevents the activation of RANKL-mediated signaling, ultimately downregulating osteoclast-mediated bone resorption.

While our study provides valuable insights into the effects of Gram-negative bacterial LPS stimulation in RBMCs, several limitations should be acknowledged. The experimental design included a 3-day pre- and post-treatment process, with all results obtained within a non-cytotoxic dose range. However, we were unable to provide data on the expression of TRAF6 in LPS-stimulated cells, particularly in the presence of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines.

Future studies should aim to investigate the accumulation of other receptor expressions in the treated groups compared to controls, which could further confirm the effectiveness of TLR4Ab and IFN γ Ab as pre-treatment, with IL-10 as post-treatment, as suggested in previous research.

Additionally, while osteoclastogenesis typically requires at least seven days of culture, our study stimulated osteoclast precursors for only three days to assess early-stage cellular changes. This represents a methodological limitation, as a longer culture period may be necessary to fully evaluate osteoclast differentiation. Furthermore, this study did not include microscopic imaging, which limits our ability to visually assess cellular changes and osteoclast formation. However, our ongoing research aims to address this limitation by incorporating microscopy-based analysis of osteoclast development to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the observed effects.

CONCLUSION

Previous studies on male C57BL6/J mice have established a direct link between autophagy and bone resorption. In our Swiss albino mouse model, we further demonstrate that elevated Bcl2 expression is positively correlated with LC3 activation, contributing to the downregulation of bone resorption. While treatment with the combination of TLR4Ab, IFN γ Ab, and IL-10 (as a post treatment) effectively restored macrophage phagocytic activity while suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokine production. Collectively, these findings suggest that targeting apoptotic and autophagic pathways offers a promising therapeutic strategy for mitigating LPS-induced inflammatory bone loss.

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the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA) Approval Number: IAEC-V/T/BB-16/ 2024, dated March 20, 2024]

Author's contribution: Biswadev Bishayi (BB) and Gopinath Mukherjee (GM) designed the study and designed the protocol. Gopinath Mukherjee (GM) and Sharmistha Samanta (SS) performed all the experiments, undertook the statistical analysis. The cell culture (RBMC in presence of MCSF + RANKL + LPS) experiment was done by GM and Tiyesh Paul (TP) under the supervision of Sandip Mukherjee (SM). Sreya Chattopadhyay (SC) was kind enough to provide us with the primary antibodies against Bcl2 and LC3 and also critically check the Western blot data and the discussion part of this section. BB and GM wrote the manuscript then BB approved the final manuscript.

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